

Protocol: Non-Linear Dynamics of Deviation from Genetically Predicted BMI and Mortality in the UK Biobank

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Study information

Title

Non-Linear Dynamics of Deviation from Genetically Predicted BMI and Mortality in the UK Biobank

Description

The increasing prevalence of obesity globally has led to an urgent need for improved understanding of the risk factors driving mortality, particularly the role of genetic predisposition in obesity-related outcomes (Kelly et al., 2008; Koliaki et al., 2023). Body Mass Index (BMI), a common measure of obesity, has a strong genetic component with heritability estimates ranging from 40-70% (Elks et al., 2012; Maes et al., 1997), and deviations from genetically predicted BMI may indicate underlying metabolic risk factors not captured by observed BMI alone. This project investigates whether individuals whose BMI deviates significantly from their genetically predicted BMI—derived from polygenic risk scores (PGS)—exhibit differential mortality risk. The study uses data from the UK Biobank (UKB), a large-scale biomedical database (Sudlow et al., 2015), to explore the association between deviations from genetically predicted BMI and all-cause mortality, with particular focus on the non-linear relationship between the magnitude and direction of these deviations and mortality outcomes.

Previous research has identified that both under- and overweight individuals face increased mortality risk compared to those with a BMI within the normal range (Aune et al., 2016; Kelly, Yang, Chen, Reynolds, & He, 2008). However, deviations from genetically predicted BMI might reflect more personalized metabolic thresholds, where individuals experience health risks even if their BMI appears within a healthy range by conventional standards (Neeland et al., 2019; Taylor & Holman, 2015; Wong et al., 2018). This study will model deviations from genetically predicted BMI as natural splines in Cox proportional hazards models (Wade et al., 2018) to capture the potential non-linear relationship between these deviations and mortality. Understanding these dynamics could provide new insights into personalized obesity management and mortality risk, beyond traditional BMI measures.

This research will use the UK Biobank Resource under Application Number 81520.

Objectives and hypotheses

Study Aim

The study aims to examine whether deviations from genetically predicted BMI, both above and below, are associated with increased risk of all-cause mortality.

Specific hypothesis

1. Greater deviations from genetically predicted BMI, whether above or below, will be associated with an increased risk of mortality.
2. Both observed BMI and deviation from genetically predicted BMI contribute independently to mortality risk.
3. Adjusting for observed BMI, deviations from genetically predicted BMI will still significantly impact mortality risk, indicating the unique role of genetic predisposition.

Design plan

Study type

This is an observational cohort study utilizing data from the UK Biobank. The UK Biobank cohort comprises individuals aged 37–73 recruited between 2006 and 2010. Anthropometric measurements and genetic data are linked with mortality data to explore the relationship between BMI deviations and all-cause mortality.

Observational Study. Data is collected from study subjects that are not randomly assigned to a treatment. This includes surveys, natural experiments, and regression discontinuity designs.

Blinding

No blinding is involved in this study.

Study design

The study utilizes data from the UK Biobank, a cohort of over 500,000 participants recruited between 2006 and 2010 across the UK. Participants provided detailed health, lifestyle, and genetic data through questionnaires and physical assessments. This study focuses on 305,901 participants with complete genetic, anthropometric, and mortality data. Observed BMI was measured at baseline, and genetically predicted BMI was calculated using polygenic risk scores (PGS) derived from genome-wide association studies (GWAS) data. The deviation between observed and predicted BMI was modeled as natural splines in Cox proportional hazards regression models, allowing for non-linear associations between BMI deviation and all-cause mortality.

Sampling plan

Existing data

This study uses pre-existing data from the UK Biobank, a large-scale biomedical cohort designed for health research. The UK Biobank provides extensive phenotypic and genetic data, and this study will use the subset of participants with complete information on BMI, genetic data, and mortality outcomes.

Inclusion Criteria

UK Biobank participants with:

- Available BMI data
- Genetically predicted BMI (calculated using polygenic risk scores)
- Mortality data (linked to national death registries)

Exclusion Criteria

- Individuals with missing BMI, age, sex, or mortality information
- Outliers: Individuals with BMI deviating more than 3 standard deviations from the mean
- Participants with pre-existing conditions that may confound the relationship between BMI and mortality (e.g., known diabetes, cardiovascular diseases, cancer diagnoses prior to recruitment, or those on medications for chronic conditions)

Registration prior to analysis of the data. As of the date of submission, the data exist and you have accessed it, though no analysis has been conducted related to the research plan (including calculation of summary statistics). A common situation for this scenario when a large dataset exists that is used for many different studies over time, or when a data set is randomly split into a sample for exploratory analyses, and the other section of data is reserved for later confirmatory data analysis.

Explanation of existing data

The UK Biobank is a large national cohort of participants in the UK, with data collected in a standardized format the sole purpose of providing a data resource for researchers to use for health research. All information about collection procedures, limitations, and sources of bias are well established and described by the UK Biobank resource.

Because of its size of data collected, it is near impossible to a priori see patterns in the data that might influence how the analysis will be conducted, unless specifically looked for or previously published on. In this way, we feel pre-analysis bias is minimal.

Data collection procedures

1. **BMI Measurement:** Height and weight were measured at baseline, and BMI was calculated as weight in kilograms divided by height in meters squared.
2. **Genetically Predicted BMI:** Calculated using polygenic risk scores derived from genome-wide association studies (GWAS). BMI predictions are adjusted for sex and age and represent the genetically predicted BMI based on individual genetic variants linked to BMI.
3. **Mortality Data:** Obtained through linkage with national death registries. Cause-specific mortality was recorded using ICD-10 codes, and mortality follow-up continued until December 2022.
4. **Covariates:** Data on age, sex, socioeconomic status (Townsend Deprivation Index), smoking status, physical activity, and income were collected through baseline questionnaires.

Sample size

The initial sample size consists of 305,901 UK Biobank participants with relevant data. After applying exclusion criteria (e.g., missing data, extreme BMI outliers, pre-existing conditions), the final sample size is expected to be approximately 208,146 participants.

Sample size rationale

The large sample size allows for sufficient power to detect significant associations between BMI deviation and mortality. Given that the UK Biobank dataset includes over 42,000 recorded deaths, there is ample statistical power to assess non-linear associations and explore subgroup analyses.

Variables

Measures variables

Exposure: BMI Deviation

- **Genetically Predicted BMI:** Calculated using polygenic risk scores (PGS), adjusted for age and sex.
- **Observed BMI:** Measured BMI at baseline.
- **BMI Deviation:** The difference between observed BMI and genetically predicted BMI (observed BMI - predicted BMI).

Outcome: All-Cause Mortality

- **Mortality Data:** Date of death and cause-specific mortality were obtained from national death registries.
- **ICD-10 codes:** Used to categorize causes of death.

Covariates

- **Age** (at recruitment)
- **Sex**
- **Socioeconomic Status:** Measured by the Townsend Deprivation Index.
- **Smoking Status:** Coded as “never,” “former,” or “current.”
- **Physical Activity:** Self-reported weekly engagement in light, moderate, and vigorous activities.
- **Income:** Categorized into five distinct economic brackets.

Analysis plan

Statistical models

1. **Descriptive Statistics:** Baseline characteristics (e.g., age, BMI, socioeconomic status) will be described for the overall population and subgroups defined by deviation from genetically predicted BMI.
2. **Cox Proportional Hazards Model:** Natural splines will be used to model the non-linear associations between BMI deviation and all-cause mortality. Models will be adjusted for age, sex, Townsend Deprivation Index, smoking status, physical activity, and income. The primary time-scale will be age, with time-to-event (death) measured from the date of recruitment to the date of death or the end of follow-up.
3. **Spline Terms:** Natural splines (with four degrees of freedom) will be used to capture non-linear relationships between BMI deviation and mortality risk. The number of spline knots will be determined by the Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC).
4. **Subgroup Analyses:** Analyses will be stratified by:
 - Sex
 - Smoking status (never, former, current)
 - Observed BMI categories (underweight, normal weight, overweight, obese)
5. **Sensitivity Analyses**
 - Further adjustment for observed BMI as a natural spline to explore the independent contribution of BMI deviation to mortality.
 - Exclusion of participants with extreme BMI deviations (>3 standard deviations).
 - Subgroup analysis restricted to participants with observed BMIs within the normal range

(18.5–24.9 kg/m²) to assess the impact of deviation within this group.

Transformations

Transformations will be applied to variables such as BMI deviation to ensure normality and homoscedasticity in statistical models. Natural splines will be used to allow flexible modeling of non-linear effects.

Inference criteria

- **Significance Level:** A p-value of <0.05 will be considered statistically significant. Hazard ratios (HRs) and 95% confidence intervals (CIs) will be reported.
- **Model Fit:** Likelihood ratio tests will be used to compare models (e.g., linear vs. spline models) to assess the significance of non-linear terms.

Data exclusion

Participants with pre-existing chronic conditions (e.g., diabetes, cardiovascular diseases) or those with extreme BMI deviations (>3 standard deviations) will be excluded to avoid confounding. Outliers in terms of covariates (e.g., physical activity, income) will also be assessed.

Missing data

Missing data will be handled using multiple imputation techniques where appropriate. If the proportion of missing data for a covariate is substantial, sensitivity analyses will be conducted to assess the robustness of the results.

Exploratory analyses (optional)

Additional analyses may explore whether BMI deviation patterns differ across age, sex, or socioeconomic subgroups.

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